

Chemical Components of *Pyrostegia venusta* flowers

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From the flowers of *Pyrostegia venusta* β -sitosterol, *n*-hentriacontane, acacetin-7-*o*- β -D-glucopyranoside and meso-inositol have been isolated and characterised.

CERTAIN plants belonging to *Pyrostegia* genus have been reported to contain flavonoid compounds¹. Since flowers of *Pyrostegia venusta*, a wellknown creeper, are prominently coloured and also attract insects and ants because of their sweetness, their extraction was undertaken with a view to study the nature of the constituents present in these. The flowers are available locally in abundance during the months from January to April.

The air dried petals of *Pyrostegia venusta* flowers were extracted with petroleum ether in a Soxhlet extractor. The petrol extract was found to contain carotenoids, waxy material along with a sterol identified as β -sitosterol (A). The defatted flowers were then extracted with 95% ethanol and the ethanolic extract was fractionated into petroleum ether, ether and ethyl acetate soluble fractions. From the petroleum ether soluble fraction, a colourless crystalline aliphatic hydrocarbon was obtained which was characterised as *n*-hentriacontane (B). From the ether as well as ethyl acetate soluble fraction a flavonoid glycoside (C) could be isolated. The residual solution on further concentration and maceration with ethanol gave an inositol(D).

Petroleum ether soluble fraction; β -sitosterol (A)

The combined petroleum ether extract after concentration was charged over a column of neutral alumina. The petroleum ether eluate yielded a white substance, m.p. 138°, identified as β -sitosterol by its positive reactions for sterols, acetate (m.p. 127°) and digitonide (m.p. 218°) and also by its co-chromatography with authentic sample and mixed melting point.

*Ethanolic extract; analysis of petroleum ether soluble fraction: Identification of *n*-hentriacontane (B)*

From the petroleum ether extract a colourless crystalline compound, m.p. 66°-67° was obtained by repeated crystallisation from acetone. It analysed for C₃₁H₆₄ (m/e 436). Its stability, negative reactions with bromine water and potassium permanganate suggested its saturated aliphatic nature. The compound lacked the presence of any functional groups as all the tests for different functional groups were negative. Thus it could be identified as a

long chain saturated hydrocarbon, *n*-hentriacontane. The structure is supported by IR bands (KBr) 2950, 2820, 1475, 1375, 735 and 723 cm⁻¹ and NMR (CDCl₃) signals at 9.1 τ for 6 methyl protons and 8.75 τ for 58 acyclic methylene protons.

*Analysis of ether soluble fraction: Identification of acacetin-7-*o*- β -D-glucopyranoside (C)*

From the ether soluble fraction of the ethanolic extract, a pale yellow compound, m.p. 243°-45°, molecular formula C₂₂H₂₂O₁₀, was obtained. It crystallised from ethyl acetate-petroleum ether mixture and was found to be chromatographically homogeneous. It was glycosidic in nature and its acid hydrolysis yielded an aglycone C₁₆H₁₂O₅ and a reducing sugar which was identified as D-(+)-glucose by paper chromatography and phenyl osazone derivative. The sugar : aglycone ratio was established as 1 : 1 by quantitative oxidation with periodate, in accordance with elemental analysis.

The pale yellow coloured aglycone, m.p. 260°-62°, was assigned flavone structure by the study of its UV and IR spectra, reductive reactions and also by other reactions typical of flavones. It was found to contain one methoxyl group (Zeisel, IR peaks at 2850 cm⁻¹ and 1185 cm⁻¹) and two hydroxyls as it forms a diacetate and a trimethyl ether. An examination of the UV spectra of the aglycone (λ_{max} 270 and 328 nm) indicated absence of an *o*-dihydroxyl system in positions -3' and -4' (lack of bathochromic shift with boric acid-sodium acetate reagent)², presence of a free hydroxyl group in position-7 (bathochromic shift with NaOAc)³ and a free hydroxyl in position-5 (bathochromic shift with AlCl₃)⁴. The colour reactions of the aglycone were also in conformity with the presence of two hydroxyls at positions -5 and -7. The only methoxyl group present was fixed in position -4' by the permanganate oxidation of the aglycone as well as its methyl ether, when anisic acid was isolated as one of the oxidation products in both the cases. The alkali cleavage of the aglycone produced phloroglucinol and anisic acid which finally confirmed the structure of the aglycone as 5,7-dihydroxy 4'-methoxy apigenin (acacetin).

The position of glucose moiety in the glycoside was determined by spectral shifts and complete methylation and hydrolysis of the glycoside (C) (λ_{max} 268 and 324 nm) when 5,4-dimethyl apigenin, m.p. 262° was obtained. Thus obviously the sugar moiety is attached at position-7 of acacetin. The position of attachment of glucose moiety was also confirmed by comparing the effect of added NaOAc reagent on the UV spectra of both (C) and its glycone when former showed lack of bathochromic shift. The glycoside on hydrolysis with the enzyme emulsion produced free glucose showing thereby that the glycosidic linkage is β in nature⁵. The glycoside methyl ether when subjected to periodate oxidation consumed 2 moles of per iodate and one mole of formic acid was liberated per mole of the glycoside. The sugar is, therefore, present in the pyranose form. The glycoside can thus be represented as :

(acacetin-7-O- β -D-glucopyranoside)

Acacetin and its glycosides specially 7-glucoiside (Tilianin) are known to occur widely in nature. It was first reported in *Tilia japonica* Simonka¹⁶ and later reported in many other sources.

The confirmation of the structure assigned to the above flavone glycoside (C) was achieved by its synthesis using modified Baker-Venkataraman method i.e., by condensing phloracetophenone 1 mol) with anisic anhydride (2.5 mol) in presence of potassium carbonate in acetone solution. After alkaline hydrolysis and acidification with carbon dioxide the flavone separated out. The acacetin thus obtained was condensed with acetobromo glucose in silver carbonate—pyridine medium, when acacetin-7-O- β -D-glucopyranoside was obtained which was found to be identical with natural sample by chromatography and mixed m.p.

Analysis of cyclitol fraction (D)

From the residual aqueous alcoholic extract a colourless compound (D), m.p. 223°–24° was isolated. Its purity and homogeneity was confirmed by paper and thin layer chromatography. The compound analysed for $C_6H_{12}O_6$ (m/e 180) and was found to be saturated. Evidently it appeared to be a sugar but this possibility was ruled out as it did not respond to Molisch test and other tests characteristic of reducing sugars. It formed an acetate, m.p. 216° and *O*-acetyl percentage corresponded to six hydroxyl groups (IR peak at 3500 cm^{-1} for -OH group). The molecular formula, therefore, could be written as $C_6H_6(OH)_6$ which corresponds to the parent

hydrocarbon C_6H_{12} , thereby suggesting the presence of one alicyclic ring in the compound. The presence of ring system in the compound was further confirmed by nitric acid oxidation of the compound followed by treatment with alkali whereby potassium salt of tetrahydroxy quinone (I) and dipotassium salt of rhodizonic acid (II) were obtained.

Thus the compound (D) could be an inositol having the structure (III).

Periodate oxidation of the compound also confirmed the presence of six hydroxyl groups in a six membered alicyclic ring i.e., the compound is an inositol. There are nine different stereoisomeric forms of inositol, each having its own characteristic melting point. The melting point of the natural compound agreed with that of meso-inositol. The mixed m.p. and co-chromatography with the authentic sample further proved the validity of the conclusion. Based on these facts the following configurational formula could be assigned to the compound :

Experimental

The fresh flower of *Pyrostegia venusta* were collected in the month of March from the University campus.

Extraction

The fresh flower petals (2 kg) were extracted with petroleum ether (40°–60°) in Soxhlet extractor

(Fraction I). The defatted flowers were subsequently extracted under reflux with ethanol (3×4 l) in a round bottom flask and the ethanolic extract was concentrated under reduced pressure. The concentrated extract was then extracted exhaustively with petroleum ether (Fraction II), ether and ethyl acetate (Fraction III) in a liquid-liquid extractor and the three fractions along with the residual aqueous alcoholic extract (Fraction V) were concentrated separately.

Fraction I (β -sitosterol)

The concentrated petroleum ether extract, when kept in the refrigerator (3 days) gave a brown substance. The mother liquor was decanted off. It contained a mixture of carotenoids as shown by paper chromatography and colour reactions. The brown crude product was chromatographed over neutral alumina and elution of the column with petroleum ether-benzene mixture gave a white compound, m.p. 138° (compound A). (Found: C, 83.92; H, 12.32. Calc. for $C_{29}H_{50}O$: C, 84.06; H, 12.08%). It gave colour reactions of steroids and was identified as β -sitosterol (acetate, m.p. 127°, digitonide, m.p. 220°). This was confirmed by co-chromatography with authentic sample (silica gel G, benzene ethyl acetate 9:1; spray, $2NH_2SO_4$).

Fraction II (*n*-hentriacontane)

The petroleum ether was completely evaporated and the syrupy liquid obtained was dissolved in boiling acetone. On cooling a colourless compound separated which was further purified by repeated crystallisation with acetone, m.p. 66°–67° (Compound B). (Found: C, 85.24; H, 14.32; Calc. for $C_{31}H_{64}$: C, 85.32; H, 14.68%). The IR absorption spectrum showed peaks at 2950, 2820, 1475, 1375, 735 and 723 cm^{-1} . NMR spectrum showed signals at 9.17 and 8.75 τ .

Fraction III (Acacetin-7-O- β -D-glucopyranoside)

The ether and ethyl acetate soluble fractions were both found to be containing an identical substance by chromatographic studies. The combined extract was dehydrated with magnesium sulphate, it was concentrated and the residue obtained crystallised from ethyl acetate-petroleum ether mixture as a pale yellow solid, m.p. 243°–45° (compound C). The paper chromatography (Whatman No. 1, BAW (4:1:5) spray $-NH_3/UV$) and TLC (silica gel C, $CHCl_3:CH_3OH$, 9:1; $2NH_2SO_4$) revealed homogeneity of the compound. It gave positive Molisch test and responded to colour reactions of flavones.

Acid hydrolysis: On hydrolysis it gave a yellow colour aglycone, m.p. 260°–62° and D-(+)-glucose (phenyl osazone, m.p. 203°).

Aglycone: The aglycone crystallised from ethyl acetate petroleum ether mixture as pale yellow prisms, m.p. 260°–62°, gave characteristic colour reactions of flavones (Found: C, 67.48; H, 4.84. Calc. for $C_{16}H_{12}O_5$: C, 67.60; H, 4.22%). It has one methoxyl group (Found: OCH_3 , 9.8%; Calc. for $C_{15}H_{10}O_4$ (OCH_3), 10.9%). Acetylation of the

aglycone with Ac_2O and $NaOAc$ in the usual manner gave a diacetate, m.p. 202° (Found: $COCH_3$, 22.4%. Calc. for $C_{16}H_{10}O_5(COCH_3)_2$, 23.36%). Methylation of the aglycone with $(CH_3)_2SO_4 \cdot K_2CO_3$ yielded a trimethyl ether m.p. 154°–55°. (Found: OCH_3 , 28.5%. Calc. for $C_{15}H_7O_2(OCH_3)_3$, 29.80%).

Permanganate oxidation: The aglycone as well as its methyl ether on oxidation with $KMnO_4$ gave anisic acid, m.p. 181°–82° (lit. m.p. 184°) [co-chromatography, *n*-butanol saturated with NH_3 , spray-bromophenol blue].

Alkali cleavage: The aglycone with alkali (50%) for 6 hr. gave anisic acid and phloroglucinol, m.p. 217°–19° (co-chromatography, BAW, 4:1:5, spray- $FeCl_3$).

Periodate oxidation: The glycoside methyl ether (0.02 g) was dissolved in ethanol (50 ml, 50%) and treated with sodium metaperiodate (25 ml, 0.1M). The reaction mixture was allowed to stand for 48 hr. A blank was prepared similarly. The periodate consumed and the formic acid liberated were estimated by the titrimetric method of Jones *et al.*⁷

For each mole of glycoside: Moles of periodate consumed = 2.1., Moles of formic acid produced = 1.0.

Emulsion hydrolysis: The glycoside (0.02 g) was hydrolysed using emulsion prepared from sweet almonds⁸. The hydrolysis was affected by warming the compound with emulsion solution at 50° for half an hour over a water bath and the reaction mixture was allowed to stand for 24 hr. at room temperature. The hydrolysate was found to contain D-(+)-glucose (Paper chromatography).

Methylation and hydrolysis: The glycoside (C) (0.05 g) in acetone (40 ml) was methylated in usual manner by heating with dimethyl sulphate (1 ml) and anhy. K_2CO_3 (5 g) for 3 hr. under reflux. The resulting methylated glycoside derivative was hydrolysed with 7% aq. H_2SO_4 yielding partially methylated aglycone (m.p. 262°).

Synthesis

Phloroacetophenone: A stream of dry HCl gas was passed through an ice cold solution of phloroglucinol (6 g), acetonitrile (3 g) and fused zinc chloride (2 g) in dry ether (25 ml). The ketimine salt separated was hydrolysed with boiling water (100 ml) to get phloroacetophenone, m.p. 219° (lit. 219°).

Anisic anhydride: A solution of thionyl chloride (2 ml) in anhydrous ether (15 ml) was gradually added with shaking to a suspension of anisic acid (10 g) in ether (30 ml) and pyridine (4 ml), the whole being cooled in ice. The anhydride separated after trituration with ice cold dil. HCl and $NaHCO_3$, m.p. 96° (lit. 99°).

5:7-dihydroxy 4'-methoxy flavone (acacetin)

Phloroacetophenone (1.5 g), anisic anhydride (6.5 g), freshly ignited K_2CO_3 (6 g) were taken up in dry acetone (100 ml) and the solution refluxed for 36 hr. Acetone was filtered off from inorganic matter and distilled under reduced pressure. The residue was

shaken with water (100 ml) and filtered. The precipitate obtained was refluxed with Alc. KOH solution (5%, 25 ml) for 20–25 min when a clear solution was obtained. Alcohol was removed under diminished pressure and the residue was taken up in water (30 ml). This aqueous solution was mixed with aqueous filtrate (100 ml) obtained above and CO₂ was passed through this solution for 3–4 hr till it was acidic. Flavone precipitated out from this solution, it was filtered and crystallised from ethyl acetate petroleum ether mixture as pale yellow crystals, m.p. 260°–61° (lit. 261°–63°).

Acacetin-7-O-β-glucopyranoside

Acacetin (0.1 g) and acetobromoglucose (0.15 g) were dissolved in pyridine (8 ml), thereafter Ag₂CO₃ (0.3 g) were added. The reaction flask was kept at 0° continuously for 5 hr. After that the solution centrifuged and the filtrate poured in acetic acid solution (10%, 100 ml) and kept in freeze overnight. The precipitate obtained was centrifuged and crystallised from ethyl acetate-petroleum ether, m.p. 243°–45°.

Fraction IV (meso-inositol)

The residual aqueous alcoholic extract was concentrated on a water bath, when a thick brown syrup was obtained. It was macerated with alcohol. An almost colourless solid was obtained, m.p. 223°–24° (compound D) (Found : C, 40.30; H, 6.80, Calc. for C₆H₁₂O₆, C, 40.0; H, 6.66%).

Ascending paper chromatography on strip of Whatman No. 1 was done using following developing solvent systems : (i) Benzene : *n*-butanol : pyridine : water (1 : 5 : 3 : 3); (ii) Isopropanol : pyridine : gl.ACOH : water (8 : 8 : 1 : 4). TLC (silica gel G) was done using the following two systems : (i) BAW (4 : 1 : 5), (ii) Isopropanol : pyridine : gl.ACOH : water (8 : 8 : 1 : 4).

In both, spots were revealed by spraying the chromatograms with a mixture of 0.1N AgNO₃ : 5N NH₃ : 2N NaOH (1 : 1 : 2) followed by exposure to steam for 1–2 min.

Acetylation with sodium acetate and Ac₂O in the usual manner gave a hexa acetate, m.p. 216° (Found :

COCH₃, 81.4%; calc. for C₆H₆O₆ (COCH₃)₆ : COCH₃, 81.94%).

Oxidation

The compound (D) 0.1 g and A.R. HNO₃ (4 ml) were taken and kept overnight. The acid was then evaporated at reduced pressure and the resulting liquid neutralised by adding K₂CO₃ when potassium salt of tetrahydroxy quinone (I) separated out as green crystalline compound.

The compound (0.1 g) and A.R. HNO₃ (1 ml) were shaken at 60° for 30 min. when all the brown fumes evolved. After 3 hr. the solution was diluted with water to 10 ml and filtered. In the filtrate potassium acetate soln. (50%) was added dropwise until one drop produced a permanent yellow colour and then 2 ml more of the potassium acetate solution was added. Air was bubbled in the flask for 30 min. after which the purple crystals of dipotassium rhodizonate formed were filtered from the dark red solution.

IR spectrum of the compound (D) showed the following main peaks : 3500, 3325, 2900, 1460, 1375, 1255, 1200, 1150, 1120, 1060, 1010, 938, 900 and 735 cm⁻¹.

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References

1. J. B. HARBORNE, *Phytochemistry*, 1967, 6, 1643.
2. L. JURD, *Arch. Biochem. Biophys.*, 1956, 63, 376.
3. L. JURD and R. M. HOBOWITZ, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1957, 22, 1618.
4. R. M. HOROWITZ, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 79, 6561.
5. D. RICHTER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 170.
6. N. MORITA, Paper read before the General Meeting of Pharm. Society of Japan, Tokyo, April 1960.
7. E. T. JONES and A. ROBERTSON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 1167.